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A HOLISTIC APPROACHES ON REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE ON MOBILE NUMBER PORTABILITY

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ABSTRACT

In today's business environment, service industry play an important role to increases the customer value in the field of telecommunication. In the recent time advance technology make easier and cheaper way to provides affordable services to the customer in telecom industry. The telecom industry is one of the fastest growing industries in India. India has nearly 200 million telephone lines making it the second largest network in the world after China , With a growth rate of 45%. Indian telecom industry has the highest growth rate in the world. Much of the growth in Asia Pacific Wireless Telecommunication Market is spurred by the growth in demand in countries like India and China. History of Indian Telecommunications it was Started in 1851 ,when the first operational land lines were laid by the government near Calcutta (seat of British power). This paper focuses on research has been done in field of Mobile Number Portability [MNP] where various dimensions like customer satisfaction, consumer preferences and awareness ,service quality. Switching behaviour, switching cost and switching intention, call rates etc. play a vital role to fulfill customer's need and expectation.

Key words - service industry, telecommunication, ,service quality and Switching behavior.

INTRODUCTION- In today's business environment, service industry play an important role to increases the customer value in the field of telecommunication. - Indian Telecom Sector has shown a huge expansion in the past decades. Due to new Economic policy Indian economy has undergone dynamic changes which were adopted in the year 1991. Mobile Number Portability [MNP] is a mechanism that allows a mobile telephone user to retain the same telephone number without changing the telephone number, after the user changes a subscribed-to mobile telephone carrier to a new mobile telephone carrier. In order to introduce MNP, it is necessary to invest considerable amounts of money into mobile carriers' facilities for installation/modification; and to fully consider user demands and effects of

introducing MNP. MNP improves users' convenience, such as free selection of mobile carriers, no time and no cost required in informing of the new telephone numbers, etc.

NEED OF review of related literature

The research has been started by the Researcher through reading. For investigation or study it is important for the researcher to be acquainted with both Previous and present available published works. So, in order to assure its familiarity, the researchers have to build upon the accumulated and the previous knowledge.

MNP refers to the ability of an users to retain their mobile number when they change their network operator/service provider services.

Objective of the Research

- 1 To study the concept of literature review.
2. To study the need and significance of literature review
3. To analyse the various dimensions associate with MNP

Research Methodology

Research Design- Descriptive Research design

Data collection – This research is based on secondary data Data's were collected through secondary sources.ie various research articles, magazines papers and websites etc.

Methods- literature survey method

Technique- content analysis technique

Overview of literature s review -on the basis of literature view concern with researcher indentifies that the various dimension in the Telecom sector specially mobile number portability

Various dimensions in mobile number portability

Dimension	Researcher	Researcher's Conclusion
<i>consumer satisfaction Switching Behavior Service Quality</i>	K Kumaresh Dr.C.Sekar	<i>Promotional offers and Service Affordability is the most important factor has a direct impact on its profitability and effectiveness.</i>
<i>Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty & company image, brand life</i>	Stergios Vranakis, p. Chatzoglou	<i>company image is the main factor affecting not only customer satisfaction, but also perceived value, service quality and customer loyalty for achieving aim.</i>
switching costs, consumer ignorance	Stefan Buehlerm Justus Haucap	four types of consumer benefits that have been examined in Switching cost
Service quality, Demographic variables such as age, gender, occupation, income.	Dr. Amulya. M Prof. D. Anand	<i>socio-demographic factor and technological advancements play vital role.</i>
<i>cost-benefit analysis , switching costs, Subscriber Awareness</i>	Atiya Faiz Khan	For reduced set up cost to analyse the total benefit.
<i>consumer preferences</i>	KULDEEP KAUR;HARITIKA ARORA	<i>Best customer services, network coverage emerge as a reason for switching behaviour between various service providers.</i>
<i>consumer preferences , service quality & brand image</i>	Chintan Shah	service quality & brand image, service charges and plan and network customers to shape their preference for MSP.
Service Quality	G. N. Satish Kumar, H. Vani, S. Vandana	Intention to switch mobile service providers PREVENT through service quality
Customer expectation Customer Satisfaction	Malhotra Gunjan, Mukherjee Amitava,	<i>specific factors Like Tariff rates And network coverage fulfill the customer expectation.</i>
<i>switching behavior , Service Quality , consumer satisfaction</i>	Habib , M. Salleh, Abdullah	switching cost-building strategy to minimize the switching behaviour

Portability

<i>perceived performance and expectations, service encounters</i>	Vijay KumarPandey, Praveen sahu	<i>the basic core service concept develop</i>
Consumer Preferences, Consumer Satisfaction	R.C.S. RAJPUROHIT, DR. M.L.VASITA	Consumers prefer on the basis of call tariffs, network coverage and value added services.
Customer loyalty; Customer retention, Customer satisfaction	Gerpott, Wolfgang Rams	customer side variables reflecting specific individual customer goals and motivations
Customer loyalty; Customer satisfaction; Switching barrier	Kim,park & jyong	to maximize customer satisfaction and the switching barrier in order to enhance customer loyalty.
Switching Behaviour, Customer satisfaction.	K. Kumaresh and S.Praveena	identify the major factors [tariff rates] switching behavior of mobile number portability.
Subscriber attitude	Tiamiyu ,Abdramon	the demographic variables, age had the strongest influence on subscriber attitudes
Switching Behaviour	M.Sathish , K.Santhosh Kumar	Consumers preferences given on the basis of call tariffs, network coverage and value added services.
competitive behavior competitive position	Smith, Ferrier, & Ndofor, 2001).	The results show that competitors gain market share when they follow competitive strategies.
Switching barrier, Switching behavior	Kim,& dounq shin	Customer satisfactions, switching barriers, and demographics significantly affect subscribers' intent to switch.
CONSUMERS' AWARENESS consumers' satisfaction	DR. M VS.SRINIVASA RAO , G. ARUNA JYOTHI	level of consumer satisfaction depends on the demographic characteristics , the social change is not significant with their age,

Conclusion- Telephone services were introduced in India in 1881. Considering the fact that India and China have almost comparable populations, India' slow mobile penetration offers huge scope for growth. In the recent time advance technology make easier and cheaper way to provides affordable services to the customer in telecom industry.in telecom sector shows tremendous growth rate approximately 45% in current time span of 4 to 5 years. There are

so many change in this sector due to advance technology. Sas per the need of consumer they want esay and convenient services from operators. Telthrough company also want to retain customer through better service provide .In this context it must to analysed the recent and past literature survey for indentified various dimensions in mobile number portability. in this paper various dimension associated with MNP are found.some of the researcher identified various dimensions which support customer behaviours. Trough this literature perspective we know the work done by the Indian researchers and others researchers on fields of MNP with some loyal aspects.

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